

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Towards best practices in AGI safety and governance: A survey of expert opinion" (~applied stream)

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ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: "Towards best practices in AGI safety and governance: A survey of expert opinion"^[1]. This paper “finds broad support for nearly all proposed safety practices across AGI labs, governments, and civil society” (evaluator 1). Evaluation 2 was done through our “applied and policy stream”, described [here](#), and involved a ~minor conflict of interest (see below). Both evaluators rated the paper highly and found this work valuable and meaningful for policy and discussions of AI safety. They also highlighted important limitations (including sampling bias, classification of practices, interpretation of results, and abstract agreement vs. real-world implementation) and gave suggestions for improvement. To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Evaluator 1](#)
2. [Evaluator 2](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote¹)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a ‘scale of journals’, what ‘quality of journal’ should this be published in?² *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Evaluator 1	70	4.0
Evaluator 2	75** ³	NA

See “[Metrics](#)” below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators’ ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).⁴

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries

Anonymous evaluator 1

This insightful and policy-relevant paper brings empirical grounding to AGI safety measures by assessing expert consensus. It finds broad support for nearly all proposed safety practices across AGI labs, governments, and civil society. Key limitations [of the paper] include potential sampling bias – particularly over-representation of safety-minded respondents – and the challenge of interpreting abstract agreement as indicative of real-world implementation. Still, the study offers valuable input for policymakers and contributes meaningfully to discussions on AGI safety.

Anonymous evaluator 2

This paper makes a valuable contribution to AGI safety by identifying areas of consensus in best practices, with implications for standards-setting. While the methodology is rigorous, more justification is needed for the selection and classification of the 50 practices. Potential biases—particularly AGI labs endorsing their own practices—should be better addressed. Organizing and contextualizing practices more clearly would aid practitioners. The interpretation of results should in some occasions be caveated with what the agreement gathered itself affords, and avoid going beyond that. Overall, this paper makes a great first step toward best practices for AGI and sets the grounds for important future work on the topic.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1 Anonymous		Evaluator 2** Anonymous	
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*
Overall assessment ⁵	70	(60, 80)	75**	(65, 85)
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁶	70	(65, 75)	80	(70, 90)
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁷	80	(75, 85)	70	(60, 80)

Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁸	70	(65, 75)	70	(60, 80)
Logic & communication ⁹	85	(80, 90)	80	(70, 90)
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹⁰	65	(50, 80)	80	(70, 90)
Real-world relevance ^{11, 12}	90	(80, 100)	70	(60, 80)
Relevance to global priorities ^{13, 14}	90	(80, 100)	70	(60, 80)

**COI issue: Evaluator 2 is a co-author with the first author in a paper with over ten authors. Due to their recent work engagements, they also have some professional ties with at least two of the other co-authors.

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1	
	Anonymous	
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	4.0	(3.5, 4.5)
What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	3.5	(3.1, 4.0)
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 	

Claim identification and assessment (summary)

For the full discussions, see the corresponding sections in each linked evaluation.

	Main research claim ¹⁵	Belief in claim ¹⁶
Evaluator 1 Anonymous	That a majority of AGI governance experts exhibit consensus in supporting 49 out of 50 specific safety-related policies and practices.	I fully believe the claims presented (over 90% probability of the claim being true).

Evaluation manager's discussion, our process

Conflict of Interest

Evaluator 2 is a co-author with the first author in a paper with over ten authors. Due to their recent work engagements, they also have some professional ties with at least two of the other co-authors.'

Issues meriting further evaluation (or consideration in future work

A number of issues were raised in the bespoke evaluation notes that were not discussed (much) by the evaluators and might be worthy of further evaluation, or of consideration by the authors and future researchers in designing follow-up work. These include:

- *Question design* (acquiescence bias, priming, order effects, etc.; reverse coding and other potential remedied)
- Patterns of *non-response* to certain questions
- Was the survey set up to provide strong 'value of information' (considering likely prior beliefs, and costs and benefits of safety practices)?
- If the paper is largely about "demonstrating a case that AI people agree on this to regulators" we might want to encourage a red-teaming approach to this
- *Lack of prioritisation or ranking between questions*: Experts evaluate each statement independently, without providing numerical scores for effectiveness, making it impossible to compare and prioritize various proposals. For example, more people might believe that Proposal A should be implemented than Proposal B, yet all of those who support both may consider Proposal B to be more impactful than Proposal A. This nuance is not captured in the current approach. Could or should this be addressed in the future?

Why we chose this paper

From our prioritization notes:

This paper aims to survey the opinions of 50 leading experts on 50 potential best practices to promote AGI safety and governance. Experts rated each potential statement on a 5 point Likert scale. Experts broadly support all practices listed, although some receive higher mean ratings and have lower disagreement.

The paper has received a moderate amount of attention (21 citations and GovAI is a large player in the AI governance space).

Extensively mentioned at [Long list of AI questions — EA Forum](#)

This is the kind of paper that I think could benefit from review from social scientists.

How we chose the evaluators

We looked for (and found) evaluators with both survey methods/social science expertise and contextual understanding of the AGI safety issues. We also sought balance in terms of the evaluators' known positions on the 'severity of AI safety concerns' question. (We further discuss what we were looking for in evaluators in the shared "[bespoke notes](#)".)

Evaluation process

We shared [these "bespoke notes"](#) with the evaluators, including some suggestions on issues they may wish to focus on.

The authors were kept informed about the process, but declined to respond ("we're unusually busy at the moment"). As always, if they choose to respond in future, we will incorporate their response in this package.

Other relevant work

We refer readers to a recent work with a similar spirit to the one evaluated here (https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5021463), which provides complementary insights. That work focuses on measures to mitigate systemic risks associated with general-purpose AI models, rather than addressing the AGI scenario considered in this paper, though some of the proposed measures partially overlap.

References

1. Schuett, J., Dreksler, N., Anderljung, M., McCaffary, D., Heim, L., Bluemke, E., & Garfinkel, B. (2023). Towards best practices in AGI safety and governance: A survey of expert opinion. arXiv:2305.07153. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2305.07153>

Footnotes

1. We asked them to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice. [↵](#)

2. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). [↵](#)

3. COI issue: Evaluator 2 is a co-author with the first author in a paper with over ten authors. Due to their recent work engagements, they also have some professional ties with at least two of the other co-authors. [↵](#)

4. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)

5.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

[↵](#)

6. “Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?”

This was on the newer form only [↵](#)

7.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

[↵](#)

8. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? [↵](#)

9. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↵](#)

10.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

└

11.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

└

12.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" └

13. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? └

14.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" └

15.

The evaluator was given the following instructions:

Identify the most important and impactful factual claim this research makes – e.g., a binary claim or a point estimate or prediction.

Please state the authors' claim precisely and quantitatively. Identify the source of the claim (i.e., cite the paper), and briefly mention the evidence underlying this. We encourage you to explain why you believe this claim is important, either here, or in the text of your report. ↵

16. Evaluators were asked: To what extent do you *believe* the claim you stated above? Feel free to express this either a. in terms of the probability of the claim being true, b. as a credible interval for the parameter being estimated, or c. however you feel comfortable. ↵

References

1. Schuett, J., Dreksler, N., Anderljung, M., McCaffary, D., Heim, L., Bluemke, E., & Garfinkel, B. (2023). *Towards best practices in AGI safety and governance: A survey of expert opinion* (Version 1). Version 1. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2305.07153> ↵